

THE ORTHOGRAPHY OF THE COMPOUND NOUNS IN THE MACEDONIAN LANGUAGE – IMPLICATIONS IN TEACHING ORTHOGRAPHY

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Abstract:

The orthography of every language including the Macedonian is a set of rules that presents the language in written form. Bearing in mind that the language reflects all phenomena of the social life, it is clear that the orthography should constantly be complemented and renewed, explained and précised in order to address the needs of its users. The new edition of the Orthography of the Macedonian language (2015) brings in changes, supplements and provides accurate information in all of the chapters of the last edition of the Orthography (1998). This represents a solid base for improving and equaling the written practice, especially regarding the orthographic rules of the compound nouns. The aim of the paper is to analyze some rules for connected writing (without hyphen) of the compound nouns in the Orthography from 1998 regarding their preciseness, clearness and possibility for double interpretation. These rules are compared with the same rules in the new edition from the Orthography (2015) in order to get an insight into the changes, supplements and the correctness, and then the rules from the new edition are analyzed regarding their preciseness, clearness and possibility for double interpretation. The research has qualitative paradigm (content analysis) and descriptive design. A nonstructural interview has been conducted with 100 teachers from the primary, secondary and the higher education. The methods for data processing and gaining scientific conclusions are analysis, comparison and synthesis. The results from the research show that beside the efforts in the new edition of the Orthography to make the explanations logic and simple in order to be accessible for a larger number of user, still the explanations open dilemmas that may lead to double

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interpretation, especially in teaching orthography of the Macedonian language. This has an impact on the orthographic competencies of the Macedonian language teacher.

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1. Introduction

The development of the society and the language is mutually connected. Every language changes inevitably to address the needs of its users. In the last twenty years, because of the globalization processes, in the Macedonian language we can notice a large number of words, mostly from the English language, whose orthography shows inequality in the written practice. Bearing in mind that the last update of the Macedonian language's orthography is done almost twenty years ago, we can clearly notice the need of its supplement once again. In this sense, the new edition of the Orthography from 2015 is a reply to this need. According to its creators it *“does not deviate from the already stipulated directions given in the previous editions of the Orthography, that were established from its first authors”* Blaže Koneski and Krum Tošev, and then from Božidar Vidoeski, Todor Dimitrovski, Kiril Koneski and Radmila Ugrinova-Skalovska (Orthography, 2015: preface). Therefore, with a pleasure, we can notice that the new edition of the Orthography really supplements and explains many dilemmas connected with certain orthographic rules, which are present in its previous editions. In the same time, the new edition introduces new orthographic rules, especially regarding the lexis that is characteristic for the conditions in which the development of the Macedonian society occurs. Hence, we can see the importance and the usefulness of the new edition for all that are engaged with the Macedonian language in any way and its contribution for equaling the written practice. This has surely a great impact in teaching orthography. It will affect the building of the orthographic competencies of the Macedonian language teacher in future.

One of the most extensive parts in the Orthography is the part that regulates the orthographic rules for compound nouns that are written connected (without hyphen). The past written practice shows that various orthographic decisions refer exactly to these nouns. Therefore, the aim of the paper is to made an analysis of certain rules that regulates the orthography of the compound nouns that are written connected (without hyphen) in the Orthography from 1998 regarding their clearness, preciseness and possibility for dual interpretation. Then, these rules are compared with the same rules in the Orthography from 2015 in order to get an insight whether the explanations resolve the dilemmas that are introduced with the edition from 1998. In the same time,

the new rules in the Orthography from 2015 are analyzed again regarding their preciseness and possibility for dual interpretation.

2. Review of the literature

In continuance, we aim to indicate the relevance of the topic that is elaborated, and therefore we list a survey of the research that has been conducted from Macedonian researchers, regarding the orthography of the connected written (without hyphen) compound nouns.

Part of the written materials refers to contrastive studies of the orthography of the compound nouns in the Macedonian language and the other foreign languages. Cvetkovski (in Makarijoska, 2009, no. 531) in his work: *“Translation of the English compound nouns in the Macedonian”* elaborates a very significant segment of the orthography of those compound nouns that are directly taken from the English language and that are only transcribed. The compound nouns in the German and in the Macedonian language are analyzed by Simoska (2010) in her work: *“Contrastive studies: Compound nouns in the German and the Macedonian language”*. Among other issues, the author addresses the orthography of the compound nouns directly taken from the German language.

Part of the written materials indicates the need of introducing changes and supplements in the already existing orthographic rules. Januševa (under review) in her work: *“The use of dash and hyphen as punctuation and orthographic marks in the newspaper sub-style of the Macedonian standard language”* shows the clear difference between the dash as an orthographic and punctuation mark and the hyphen as an orthographic mark. She indicates the need of further concretization and precision of the orthographic rules of compound nouns and suggests that this will reduce the possibility of dual interpretation. She also stresses the importance of introducing new rules regarding the orthography of the compound nouns, as well as new examples that will refer to the need of the modern society. Jurukovska (2016) in her master thesis: *“The dash and the hyphen in the written practice of the modern Macedonian language”*, also shows the difference between the already mentioned marks, i.e. the dash and the hyphen. She analyzes extensive material that refers to four functional styles in the Macedonian language (scientific, administrative, journalistic and literary). She demonstrates significant number of deviations regarding the orthography of the compound nouns: *radio-drama* [*radio drama*] (Nastavna programa, – Teaching Curriculum, 2008: 12); *avto – raketata* [*the auto rocket*] (Velkova, Jovanovska, 2010: 91); *Radio–aparati* [*radio set*] (“Nova Makedonija” – New Macedonia, 2013: 8). According to Jurukovska, the orthographic

rule that regulates the orthography of this type of compounds (Pravopis – Otrhography, 1998: 50, p. 107, a, b) does not contain precise information and that it is not easy to determine the foreign origin of the first component.

This survey shows that there are contrastive studies of the orthography of the compound nouns and that there are studies, which indicate the need of introducing new rules. Therefore, the topic is important for everybody that is concerned with the Macedonian language in any way, not only for the linguists. The written practice regarding the orthography of these compounds shows different deviations from the orthographic norms and therefore there is a need for further explanations and preciseness of the orthographic rules. In this sense, the Orthography from 2015 contains changes that have essential meaning regarding the preciseness and explanations of the rules for connected written compounds (without hyphen), as well as for certain dilemmas connected with these explanations.

3. Methodology of the research

In light of the paper's objectives, at first we analyze certain rules for connected written compounds (without hyphen) listed in the Orthography from 1998 (Pravopis – Orthography, 1998: 49 – 62). Part of these rules is stable enough and established in the written practice. We can confirm this notice with our experience as native speakers and researchers of the modern Macedonian language. Then we use written materials from the electronic editions of the Macedonian daily newspapers: "Vest" (News), "Dnevnik" (Every day) and "Utrinski vesnik" (Morning journal); extensive written material, for ex., textbooks, various written materials from the students; as well as nonstructural interviews with 100 teacher of the Macedonian language in primary, secondary and higher education. Then, these rules are compared with the same rules from the new edition of the Orthography (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 57 – 67) in order to get an insight of the changes, explanations and supplements that have been introduced in the new edition, regarding the rules and the examples. In the same time, we show whether these explanations make the rules more precise in order for them to be logical and simple.

Nevertheless, part of the rules for the orthography of the compounds introduced in the edition from 1998 is not clear enough and there is a need for additional explanations, primarily because there is a possibility for them to be interpreted dually and implemented in the written practice in different ways. Confirmations for these claims are the already mentioned sources in the first paragraph of point 3. In accordance with that, certain rules for connected written compounds (without hyphen)

in the Orthography from 1998 are analyzed regarding their preciseness, clearness and possibility for dual interpretation. Then, these rules are compared with the same rules in the new edition of the Orthography from 2015 in order to get information whether the new edition offers more precise and clear explanations, whether the rules are supported with appropriate examples and whether the explanations contribute for them to be logical and simple. In the same time, the rules from the new edition of the Orthography are analyzed again regarding whether they are clear and precise enough and whether they open a possibility for dual interpretation.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Compound nouns that are written connected (without hyphen)

A) The compound nouns which components are connected with linking vowels *-o-* and *-e-*: *basnopisec* [fabulist], *vetrokaz* [wind gauge], *vodovod* [plumbing], *drovod* [alley], *kolovoz* [roadway], *rakopis* [handwriting], *stihotvorba* [poem], *sončogled* [sunflower], *ribolov* [fishing], *očevidec* [eyewitness] etc. are written connected without hyphen. The following words have the same orthography: *jugoistok* [southeast], *jugozapad* [southwest], *severoistok* [northeast], *severozapad* [northwest] (Pravopis – Orthography, 1998: 49, p. 106). This rule is quite clear: there are two components, for ex., *south* and *east*, *hand* and *write* or, *eye* and *sight* (noun + noun, noun + verb or, noun + noun) and the compound derived from them is written with linking vowels *-o-* or *-e-* between the components. Bearing in mind our experience as native speakers and researchers of the Macedonian language, we can surely claim that the written practice does not show any problems in implementation of this rule. This means that the rule is stable enough and that it is well established in the written practice. We can find a confirmation for this notice in the following: the electronic editions of the already mentioned newspapers do not contain examples that are written wrong in the period from 2010 to 2016; then various textbooks, different written material from students; the nonstructural interviews with the teachers of the primary, secondary and higher education in the Republic of Macedonia. However, it is obvious that this rule needs further explanation regarding the components of the compound, i.e. the components can refer to independent words as well as to roots of words from various word groups.

The new edition of the Orthography provides additional explanation of this rule: the two components of the compound are in an unequal relation – the first component explains the meaning of the second. According to the new edition, the first component is a root of words from various word groups and this is a strong confirmation that our claim for supplements of the rule is correct. What is missing in the new edition as in the

one from 1998 is the explanation that the first component, beside root can be an independent word too, for ex.: a noun: *stihotvorba* [poem]. The component *stih* [verse] is an independent noun. As for the second component, the new edition explains that it can be an independent noun, for ex., *lov* [hunt] in *ribolov* [fishing], or derived noun form without independent use, for ex., *-videc* or *-ljubec* [-videc or -ljubec] in *očevidec* and *čovekoljubec* [eyewitness and philanthropist]. The compound signifies one concept (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 57, p. 100). After this explanation, the segments a, b and c are given. The examples in the Orthography from 1998 are kept completely but there are also new examples that reflect that actual social reality. There are examples for the orthography of the compound nouns with linking vowel *-o-*: *mostogradba* [building a bridge], *jugonostalgičar* [person that has homesickness for the Former Yugoslav Republic] etc. Then, there are examples for the orthography of the compounds with linking vowel *-e-*: *očevidec* [eyewitness], *jajcevod* [oviduct], *srcebol* [heart pain] etc. At the end, there are examples for the orthography of compound noun got with direct adhesion of the components: *domazet* [husband of the daughter who lives with the bride's parents after the wedding] *doma* [home] + *zet* [husband of the daughter], *imenden* [name day] *ime* [name] + *den* [day], *rodenden* [birthday] etc. (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 57, p. 100, a, b and c). The additional explanation of what the second component represents introduces some dilemmas.

Let us take an example: the compound *patokaz* [signpost]. We can notice that the second component of this compound is *-kaz* [-kaz]. According to the explanation, it should be comprehended as derived noun form that cannot have an independent use. The Dictionary of the Macedonian language with Serbo-Croatian interpretations (RMJ, 1986) and the Monolingual Dictionary of the Macedonian language (TRMJ, 2006) confirm that this form does not have independent use. Then, how should we understand the component *-kaz* [-kaz]? The backformation of the Macedonian word contains cases with zero derivation, i.e. deriving nouns from verbs with zero derivational suffix, for ex., *od* [walk] from *odi* [to walk], *čekor* [step] from *čekori* [to step] etc., but these derivations have an independent use (Koneski, 1995: 40 – 41). Therefore, it is wrong to claim that the component *-kaz* represents derivational noun form, though it is true that it does not have independent use. The morphemic analysis of the form *kažuva* [to tell] confirms our thinking that *-kaž* is in fact the base of the verb *kažuva* [to tell] and *-uva* is the suffix to derive verbs that show unfinished action from verbs that show finished action [*kaže* – *kažuva* – said – say]. Hence, the second component of this compound as well as of the compounds *rakopis* [handwriting] and *vetrokaz* [wind gauge] is in fact verb base and not derived noun form without independent use or independent noun. Further, we can take as an example the compound noun *sončogled* [sunflower].

According to the additional explanation we should comprehend the form *-gled* [-*gled*] as a derived noun form without independent use or as independent noun. The Dictionary of the Macedonian language with Serbo-Croatian interpretations (RMJ, 1986: 100) shows that the form *gled* [*sight*] is present as an independent noun, which has use in the dialects. The Monolingual dictionary of the Macedonian language (TRMJ, 2003) does not register this form. From here, the dilemma arises, what is the form *gled* [*sight*], independent noun or base of the verb? This form has dialect use, it is not present in the TRMJ, it is not present in the electronic editions of the above mentioned newspaper, the nonstructural interviews with the Macedonian language teachers confirms that the form *gled* [*sight*] in the modern Macedonian language does not have an independent use. The morphemic analysis of the form *gleda* [*to see*] shows again that the form *gled-* [*sight*] is the base of the verb. This notice can be confirmed with the examples *domazet* [*husband of the daughter who lives with the bride's parents after the wedding*], *imenden* [*name day*] etc., where the second components are in fact an independent nouns *zet* [*husband of the daughter*] and *den* [*day*]. However, in the form *bratučed* [*cousin*] the second component is the part *-čed* [-*čed*] which is neither an independent noun nor a derived noun form. The morphemic analysis shows that *-čed* [-*čed*] is in fact the base of the noun *čedo* [*child*]. Therefore, the additional explanation in the new edition of the Orthography should be corrected. It should be stressed that the second component of these compounds can be independent noun: *lov* [*hunting*] in *ribolov* [*fishig*]; derived noun form without an independent use: *-ljubec* [-*ljubec*] in *čovekoljubec* [*philanthropist*]; as well as base of the verb: *-kaz* [-*kaz*] in *patokaz* [*signpost*] and the base of the noun: *-čed* [-*čed*] in *bratučed* [*cousin*].

The examples of the compounds with linking vowel *-e-* in the new edition of the Orthography also show dilemmas. In the new edition of the Orthography, it is said that these formations are rare and that they can be understood as formation got with direct adhesion of the components (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 58, p. 100, b). Hence, there is a possibility for dual interpretation. On the one hand, it can be understood that all compounds with a linking vowel *-e-* are formations got with direct adhesion of the components. On the other, it can be understood that only the listed compounds with the linking vowel *-e-* are formations with direct adhesion. Therefore, we can conclude that the additional explanation of this rule in the new edition of the Orthography will not affect its stability in the written practice. Still it has an impact in the teaching process, especially in the higher education where teaching orthographic contents should build the orthographic competencies of the future Macedonian language teacher, and therefore precise scientific explanations and conclusions are needed.

B) The rule for the orthography of the compounds that denote names of holidays in the Orthography from 1998 is within the rule 106 (Pravopis – Orthography, 1998: 49, p. 106, v) and until now we do not notice problems in its implementation in the written practice. A confirmation for this claim is the above mentioned sources in part A. In the new edition of the Orthography this rule is cited as a separate rule, the examples in the edition from 1998 are kept completely, but new examples that are written connected (without hyphen) are added too (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 58, p. 103): *Velipetok* [Great Friday], *Veličetvrtok* [Great Thursday] and *Veljasabota* [Great Saturday]. These new examples introduce the question of their orthography in case if the first component is *Veliki* [Great] and not *Veli* [Great], i.e. whether these compounds should be written connected (without hyphen): *Velikipetok* [Great Friday] or separated: *Veliki P(p)etok* [Great F(f)riday]. If we say that the compounds should be written separately then we face another dilemma: whether the second component should be written with a small or capital first letter. The written practice shows that there are various examples with a small as well as with a capital letter. For ex., *veliki petok* [Great Friday] (D, 21.10.2016); *Veliki Petok* [Great Friday] (D, 3.5.2016; Vs, 24.1.2014; Uv, 26.3.2016); *Veliki petok* [Great Friday] (D, 10.4.2015; Vs, 10.7.2014; Uv, 10.4.2015); *Veliki četvrtok* [Great Thursday] (D, 1.5.2016; Uv, 29.4.2016); *Veliki Četvrtok* [Great Thursday] (D, 17.4.2014; Uv, 18.6.2014); *Velika Sabota* [Great Saturday] (30.4.2016); *Velika sabota* [Great Saturday] (30.4.2016). Accordingly, on the one side, this separate rule for the orthography of the compounds with the component *Veli-* [Great] contributes the equal written practice. On the other, it opens the question for the orthography of the second component, i.e. whether it should be written with a small or capital first letter, in case if the first component is *Veliki* [Great]. This dilemma can be resolved if we take into consideration another rule in the new edition, i.e. the rule for writing the names of the holidays. According to this rule in the names of the holidays, capital letter is used only in the first part of the compound noun (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 49, p. 73) and in other parts that are personal names. Hence, we can conclude that the second component of the listed nouns in p. 103 should be written with a small letter. For ex.: *Veliki petok* [Great Friday], *Veliki četvrtok* [Great Thursday] and *Velika sabota* [Great Saturday] bearing in mind the analogy with the another listed examples in the rule that regulates the use of capital letter only in the first part of the compound: *Todorova sabota* [Todor's Saturday], *Ramazan bajram* [Ramazan bajram – Muslim holiday]. Therefore the teachers and researchers of the Macedonian language should take into account the fact that certain dilemmas are clarified if they have in mind another rules in the Orthography, in order to get appropriate and correct explanations.

C) The rule that regulates the orthography of the compounds which first component is a foreign element is very important because in the electronic editions of the sources cited in A, there are many hesitations in their orthography (correct and wrong orthography even in the same newspaper (Pravopis – Orthography, 1998: 50, p. 107, a, b). The Orthography list 28 foreign elements, but this is surely not a complete list. There is a need of additional explanation in this rule: the notion “foreign element” cannot be understood correctly, simply because certain of these components are frequently used and they are not perceived as foreign any more from the native speakers of the Macedonian language. For ex., the compound *fotoaparāt* [*device to take picture with*] has two components *foto* [*photo*] and *aparāt* [*device*]. Both of the elements are foreign. Even if the component *foto* [*photo*] is identified as a foreign element, the second component *aparāt* [*device*] is problematic. The form *aparāt* [*device*] origins from the Latin language (Belčev, 2002: 49), but according to the interviews conducted with the teachers, it is not perceived as a foreign element. Therefore, the explanation of the nature of the first and the second component, as well as their interpretation can affect the orthography of these compounds. Of course, we cannot reject the notion that their different orthography is because the rule is not respected. Therefore the electronic editions of the mentioned newspapers, various textbooks and extensive written material etc. show examples with correct orthography (probably because the examples are followed and not the rule) but also with the wrong orthography: *radio emisija* [*radio program*] (D, 30.8.2016, 22.12.2013; U_V, 17.5.2016, 17.3.2016, 1.4.2014, 18.6.2013, 19.10.2011; V_S, 23.3.2010); *radio-emisija* [*radio program*] (V_S, 16.12.2014) etc.

On the other side, the new edition of the Orthography lists more than 80 foreign elements as the first component of the compound. The new edition also offers many examples that reflect the everyday life of the Macedonian language’s speakers. This, sure, contributes to the equal written practice (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 59, p. 111). In the new edition, there is a more precise explanation of the first component – it is a base from a foreign language, which supplements the meaning of the second component in an attributive way. The nature of the second component in the new edition is not mentioned. Nevertheless, the given examples prove that, as it is mention in the Orthography from 1998, the second component is a domestic or a foreign word: *avtopat* (domestic) [*highway*] and *evrokomesar* (foreign) [*euro commissary*]. Except the explanation of the nature of the first component, the new edition does not provide additional explanation that will make the rule simpler. This reduces the possibility of the new edition to be approachable for most of its users. It is most probable, and this is confirmed with the conducted interview, that these compounds should be learned the way they are written. As we will see below, some examples that are part from other

rules in the new edition can be covered with this rule and that is why we insist on additional explanation. The period for implementation of this rule is too short – the new edition was published in 2015. However, we can notice that the written practice is full with examples that are listed as new in the new edition and that have wrong orthography. For ex.: *akva park* [aqua park] (Uv, 27.4.2016); *akva-park* [aqua park] (Uv, 25.3.2016, 12.2.2016); *audio zapis* [audio record] (Uv, 7.4.2016); *audio snimka* [audio shot] (Uv, 25.9.2016, 10.8.2016); *bio-dizel* [bio diesel] (Uv, 26.9.2016); *video kaseteta* [video cassette] (Uv, 25.3.2016); *video nadzor* [video control] (Uv, 3.10.2016, 1.9.2016); *video-nadzor* [video control] (Uv, 5.7.2016); *video proekcija* [video projection] (Uv, 26.9.2016); *disko klub* [disco club] (Uv, 19.9.2016); *kontra-akcija* [contra action] (D, 24.3.2016); *kontra-napad* [contra attack] (D, 31.3.2016); *kontra napad* [contra attack] (D, 9.2.2016); *krim-tehnika* [crime technique] (D, 4.11.2016); *krim tehnika* [crime technique] (D, 4.9.2016); *latino-muzika* [Latino music] (D, 20.10.2016); *mega dzvezda* [mega star] (D, 20.1.2016); *porno film* [porn film] (D, 19.5.2016) etc. There is no doubt that the short period for implementation of this rule affects the different orthography. On the other side, if we take into account that the last update of the orthography occurs 20 years ago, we are very surprised that wrong orthography of these type of compound exists even in the examples before the updating. We claim that 20 years are more than enough for the rule to be established but the examples in the written practice do not support this claim. This is a strong indicator that there is a need for additional explanation of this rule. Some examples: *video tekst* [video text] (D, 26.5.2012); *elektro-inžener* [electrical engineer] (D, 27.10.2012; Uv, 16.3.2014); *elektro- inžener* [electrical engineer] (Uv, 26.2.2016); *elektro inžener* [electrical engineer] (Uv, 1.5.2012; Vs, 13.4.2012); *elektro-industrija* [electrical industry] (Uv, 22.2.2015); *elektro industrija* [electrical industry] (Uv, 15.9.2014, 12.3.2014); *elektro motor* [electrical motor] (Uv, 18.6.2012); *kino pretstava* [cinema performance] (D, 31.3.2013, 2.1.2012; Uv, 8.9.2014); *radio-vrska* [radio connection] (D, 25.11.2015, 6.10.2014, 10.3.2010; Uv, 25.11.2015, 21.12.2014, 2.3.2010); *radio vrska* [radio connection] (Uv, 7.9.2012; Vs, 26.12.2012, 7.9.2012); *radio pretplata* [radio subscription] (Uv, 31.8.2010); *radio programa* [radio program] (Uv, 31.5.2016, 17.6.2015, 23.12.2014, 26.12.2012).

D) According to the Orthography from 1998 (1998: 51, p. 108, b) the names of the chemical compounds are written connected (without hyphen): *metilalkohol* [methyl alcohol], *oksidrat* [ohi hydrate], *sulfurovodorod* [sulfur hydrogen], *cijanvodorod* [cyan hydrogen] *cijankalium* [cyan potassium] etc. These words do not have frequent use and they are primarily connected with the chemistry, medicine etc. However, the written practice shows that this rule is well established. Still, it is worth to notice that the number of examples for chemical compounds in the Orthography (1998) is too small.

Therefore, it is hard to make an analogy for the names of other chemical compounds, i.e. there are names of chemical compound that cannot be covered with this rule.

In the Orthography from 2015, this rule is given as a separate rule (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 61, p. 113). According to the Orthography the names of the chemical compounds that contain linking vowel *-o-* are written connected (without hyphen): *bromovodorod* [bromine hydrogen], *jodovodorod* [iodine hydrogen], *sulfurovodorod* [sulfur hydrogen], *hlorovodorod* [chlorine hydrogen], *fluorovodorod* [fluorine hydrogen] etc. The names of the other chemical compounds are written separately. The examples *metilalkohol* [methyl alcohol], *oksihidrat* [ohi hydrate], *cijankalium* [cyan potassium] written connected in the Orthography from 1998, in the new edition are written separately: *metil alkohol* [methyl alcohol] *oksi hidrat* [ohi hydrate], *cijan kalium* [cyan potassium]. The following examples are written also in this way: *aluminium hlorid* [aluminum chloride], *barium sulfat* [barium sulfate], *jaglerod dioksid* [carbon dioxide] and *sulfur dioksid* [sulfur dioxide] (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 66, p. 129). Therefore, there is a change, in the new edition, a linking vowel *-o-* is introduced in the names of some chemical compound: *sulfurvodorod* [sulfur hydrogen] (1998) and *sulfur vodorod* [sulfur hydrogen] (2015). The cause for these changes, according to the creators of the new edition is the established practice in the chemistry. The number of the examples in the new edition is big, still according to these orthographic solutions, it is hard to implement analogy for the names of the other chemical compounds. If we look at the document, “Principles of the chemical nomenclature” (Lee et al., 2004) it is obvious that the language of the chemistry has its own logic and that it is difficult to cover all the names of the chemical compounds with a single rule. This document tries to make “unique international nomenclature” and “unify the principles for denominating in the various sphere of the chemistry”. It contains many recommendations for the names of the various chemical compounds and it can be seen that in listing the elements in the chemical compounds, the small, medial and big brackets have an important role. This document also refers to the most significant issue, i.e. the connected or separated orthography of the chemical compounds assumes a different way of bonding of the elements in the compound. For ex., if we write *hidrogenkarbonat* [hydrogen carbonate] it is assumed that the hydrogen is in a way tied to the carbonate part. If we write this compound separately as a two word, then it means that they are not tied (Lee et al., 2004: preface). This document indicates the various types of nomenclatures, for ex., “SiCl₄ can be denominated as *silicium tetrahlrorid* [silicon tetrachloride] (binary), *tetrahlrorosilicium* [tetra chlorine silicon] (coordinative) and *tetrahlrorosilan* [tetra chlorine sylane] (substitutive)”. The name of the one is neither “better” nor “more correct” compared with the others. All this and the names of the chemical compounds as *dikislorod heksafluoroplatinat* [dioxide hexa fluorine

platinum], *amonium natrium hidrogenfosfat* [*ammonium sodium hydrogen phosphate*] etc. show that the single rule for the orthography of chemical compounds in the new edition cannot be implemented on all chemical compounds. In this case, it is very important that a text, which contains names of chemical compounds, should be proofread by an expert familiar with the principles of the chemical nomenclature.

E) The rule 107, p. b (Pravopis – Orthography, 1998: 50) is not precise at all. It lists only examples and says, “the following words are written connected”: *kontraadmiral* [*contra admiral*], *vicekonzul* [*vice consul*], *pleksiglas* [*plexus glass*], *lajtmotiv* [*theme*] etc. It does not indicate certain regularity or generalization of the word that are written in this way. Therefore, it is understandable why the abovementioned sources in point a show a lot of dual solution for their orthography. We can notice that the same example is written connected, and separately too. The unclearness and the lack of precision in this rule are confirmed by the Macedonian language teacher.

In the new edition of the Orthography, this rule is noticed as a separate rule. According to it, certain (which means not all, there is no generalization) compound noun (the newer from the English language – which means that there are older and not from the English language) that have two foreign components are written connected. The new edition points out that in these words we have to have in mind the rules for transcription of foreign words and the rules for formation and pronunciation of compounds in the Macedonian language. Examples: *autsajder* [*outsider*], *bajpas* [*bypass*], *bekstejdž* [*backstage*], *bebisiter* [*babysitter*], *bodibilding* [*bodybuilding*], *plejbek* [*playback*] *primabalerina* [*prima ballerina*] *rentakar* [*rent a car*], *fiksidgeja* [*obsession*], *šoumen* [*show man*] etc. (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 62, 114). According to the rule, their transcription is the basic criterion for parting of these words in a separate rule. However, knowing the transcription and the rules for formation of compound nouns in the Macedonian language imply that one has to know the Macedonian and other languages as well as the formation of the words. On the one side, this indicates that the new edition cannot be used from a large number of users except for the linguists. On the other, we should bear in mind that not all linguists are synchronized regarding the transcription and the formation of the compound nouns in the Macedonian language. For ex., *autsajder* [*outsider*] contains two components from foreign origin *out* + *side*. With their transcription from the English, we get *aut-* and *-sajd* and the suffix *-er* which designates the name of subject, is added to *-sajd*. *Bilbord* [*billboard*] contains two components from foreign origin *bill-* + *-board*. With their transcription from the English in the Macedonian language, we get *bil-* and *-bord*. In these two cases, the foreign (English) origin of the components is obvious and recognizable. Still, this rule contains examples as *primabalerina* [*prima ballerina*] and *hausmajstor* [*house skilled worker*] which components do

not origin from the English. The part *prima* [*prima*] origins from the Latin language and *balerina* [*ballerina*] form the Italian (Belčev, 2002: 74, 515); *haus* [*house*] and *majstor* [*house skilled worker*] origin from the German language (Belčev, 2002: 374, 694). These words are registered in the Dictionary of the Macedonian language with Serbo-Croatian interpretations (RMJ, 1986: 1030, 1590) and they are actively used form the native Macedonian speakers more than 50 years. Therefore, it can be said that the foreign origin of the components of these two words is hard to find out. It is also not recognizable primarily because that regarding their frequent use, they are not perceived as foreign words. Therefore, it is hard to generalize in this rule. The following example also confirms the need for further explanation of this rule. The compound *ultranacionalizam* [*ultra nationalism*] means *ekstremen nacionalizam* [*extreme nationalism*] and it is covered by the rule 111, p. 61, part C. According to this rule, the first component is a base from a foreign language and it supplements the meaning of the second in an attributive way. The compound *lokalpatriotizam* [*local patriotism*] means *lokalen patriotizam* [*local patriotism*] and it is covered by the rule 114, p. 62, part E. As it is said, this rule takes into account the rules for transcription and for formation of compounds in the Macedonian language. The question arises: Which is the main criterion to separate these two words into two separate rules? It seems that these two examples do not show essential difference. *Ultra* [*ultra*] means *ekstremen* [*extreme*] and originates from the Latin (Belčev, 2002: 659), *nacionalizam* [*nationalism*] from the French; *Local* [*local*] means *from one place or region* and origins from the Latin and *patriotizam* [*patriotism*] from the Latin (Belčev, 2002: 364, 477). The components of these words are from foreign origin, they are transcribed and there is correspondence in their grammatical structure (adjective + noun). This example confirms that it is not possible to separate the two rules, 111 and 114, clearly (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 59, 62). The need for further explanation of this rule is shown in the compound *fiksidea* [*obsession*], which according to the Orthography from 1998 should be written with hyphen: *fiks-idea* [*obsession*] (Pravopis – Orthography, 1998: 52). There is no clear motivation for this change. The compound *šoumen* [*showman*] also confirms the need for further explanation and generalization. Therefore, all of the listed examples in the point E can be interpreted regarding the rule from point C, which says that the first component supplements the meaning of the second in an attributive way. They can be interpreted also regarding the rule for writing of the compounds with hyphen (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 62 – 64, 116, a, b). It says that hyphen is used for the writing of two nouns from which the one explains the other, and the determine article comes with the second component (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: vii). The explanation of these two rules is identical, the one noun explains the other, and it seems that this explanation

has no significant meaning in their clear separation. For ex., if *šoumen* [showman] is covered with the rule 114 which takes into account the transcription, we cannot see reason why the compound *šou-biznis* [show business] is covered with another rule (writing with hyphen) (Pravopis – Orthography, 2015: 63, 116, a). This especially if we have in mind that *šoumen* [showman] and *šou-biznis* [show business] are transcribed compounds and in the two cases the one component explains the other. Therefore, we expect that primarily because of the impreciseness of the rule in the Orthography from 1998, and the two rules in the Orthography from 2015 the written practice to be full of these compounds with dual orthography (correct and wrong). This is confirmed with the examples in the electronic editions of the cited newspaper. Examples: *baj-pas* [bypass] (Uv, 30.3.2016; Vs, 24.12.2015); *baj pas* [bypass] (Uv, 1.8.2015); *bodi bilding* [bodybuilding] (karas, 25.4.2015); *bor-mašina* [machine] (Uv, 29.9.2015); *bor mašina* [machine] (Pozitiv, 5.10.2016); *vice-premier* [vise premier] (Uv, 14.6.2016, 14.2.2016); *general štab* [general headquarter] (D, 11.11.2016, 11.9.2016, 3.11.2015; A1, 6.11.2016); *general-štab* [general headquarter] (Republika – Republic, 30.11.2015); *er-kondišn* [air condition] (Ms, 4.9.2015); *lajt-motiv* [theme] (D, 10.2.2015; Uv, 27.9.2016, 14.4.2016, 31.3.2016, 14.8.2015); *lajt motiv* [theme] (Uv, 23.5.2016); *lajt-šou* [light show] (D, 10.2.2016; Kafe pauza [Coffee break] 19.11.2016; Radio MOF, 12.1.2016); *lajt šou* [light show] (Uv, 1.3.2015; eMagazin, 2.7.2016; A1.on.mk, 2.2.2016); *lap top* [lap top] (D, 29.10.2016); *lap-top* [lap top] (D, 8.8.2016, 8.1.2016; Uv, 17.10.2016, 7.2.2016); *local-patriotizam* [local patriotism] (Prizma – Prism, 11.7.2016); *local patriotizam* [local patriotism] (Vs, 12.6.2016); *luna-park* [amusement park] (D, 20.11.2016, 3.7.2016; Uv, 3.7.2016, Uv, 24.4.2016); *luna park* [amusement park] (D, 11.8.2016, 15.7.2016, Uv, 28.10.2016, Uv, 19.9.2016); *mizan-scena* [misenscene] (Lelovac, 2014); *nok aut* [knock out] (Uv, 4.10.2016; Kurir – Courier, 25.11.2016); *nok-daun* [knock down] (DS; Kurir – Courier, 23.9.2016); *plej-bek* [play back] (Kurir – Courier, 28.3.2016); *renta kar* [rent a car] (Zlatna kniga – Golden book); *rent-a-kar* [rent a car] (Planet travel); *stend-baj* [stand by] (D, 6.7.2016; Uv, 19.2.2016); *stend baj* [stand by] (D, 6.6.2016; Uv, 31.10.2016); *tajm-aut* [time out] (D, 11.9.2016; Uv, 20.11.2016); *tajm aut* [time out] (Uv, 23.8.2016) etc.

5. Conclusion

The analysis and the results show that the rules for connected writing of the compounds (without hyphen) in the edition of the Orthography from 1998 are not clear and precise enough. Therefore, the written practice shows a lot of these compounds written differently, because there is a possibility for dual interpretation. The comparison with the edition of the Orthography from 2015 shows that the new edition

really provides supplements and extensive explanations as well as new examples that corresponds with the need of the modern society. However, it is obvious that some of these explanations and supplements regarding the second component of the compound are wrong. For ex., the compound nouns that have two components connected with the linking vowels *-o-* and *-e*.

Further, the new edition has a large number of examples regarding the rule for connected writing of the compounds which first component is a foreign element. Part of these examples is written wrong because the rule is not respected from the users. However, it should be mentioned that the wrong orthography of these compounds also appears due to the unclearness and impreciseness of the rule. As mentioned before, twenty years are more than enough for the rule to be established, especially regarding the examples before the updating. Their wrong orthography serves as an indicator that the rules need further concretization (one rule in the edition from 1998 and the two rules in the edition from 2015).

Regarding the orthography of the chemical compounds, there is also a need of further explanations and an inevitable presence of a proofreader and an expert who is familiar with the nomenclature in the chemistry. The single rule in the new edition cannot cover all names of the chemical compounds. The new edition indicates the need that in some cases the linguist or the teacher should call out other rules in the Orthography in order to bring scientific conclusions. This is evident in the rule for writing the compound nouns, which designate holidays.

The rules in part C and E are not clear enough. It seems that both of the rules exploit the explanations – one component is précising the meaning of the other. This is simply not enough. The rule in part C refers to the foreign origin of the one component, but the second component can have foreign origin too. The foreign origin of the components is hard to be noticed and due to their frequent use, they are not perceived as foreign any more. The rule E also refers to the compounds, which have two foreign components, but demands that their transcription and the rules for forming compound nouns in the Macedonian language should be taken into consideration. So, why are *ultranacionalizam* [*ultra nationalism*] and *lokalpatriotizam* [*local patriotism*] covered by two separate rules? They are both written connected (without hyphen), have two foreign components, are transcribed and have the same grammatical structure. Why are *šoumen* [*showman*] and *šou-biznis* [*show business*] covered by two separate rules? *Šoumen* [*showman*] is written connected and *šou-biznis* [*show business*] with a hyphen. The Orthography from 2015 does not provide precise and unambiguous explanations.

Though the new edition tries to make the Orthography approachable to a large number of users, still the explanations are neither logical nor simpler and they open

dilemmas regarding their dual interpretation. This affects teaching the orthography because it allows the future teacher of Macedonian language to face difficulties regarding the scientific explanation and unambiguous conclusions. The analysis supports the fact that the science should follow the language's development. Hence, it is inevitable that new editions of the orthography should appear constantly in order for them to be more precise and with accurate information and examples.

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